

STYLISTIC FEATURES OF PHONETIC PHENOMENA IN
ADVERTISEMENTS

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Abstract: Advertising text as a unit of advertising speech is an object of research for experts in various scientific fields. Stylistics of phonetic phenomena is an integral element of modern advertising text. The article analyzes the stylistic features of phonetic phenomena in advertisements.

Keywords: advertising, discourse, stylistics, phonetic phenomena, pragmatics, text.

The speech effect of the advertising text is realized at the expense of all its components: pictorial, sound, image, and word shell¹. However, the phonetic components play the main role in the occurrence of locution and its transition to the illocutionary stage. As long as advertising texts aim to convey conciseness, imagery, expression, and a large amount of information in a small volume, the phonetic nature can create a decisive motivational effect in most places. Therefore, it is appropriate to first examine the pragmatic aspects of advertising discourse within the framework of phonetic methodology.

It should be noted that phonetic methodology discusses the use of speech phenomena that are the object of examination of the fields of phonetics, phonology, and morphology of linguistics, for what purposes, and for what methodologically and expressively.

About the essence and function, intonation and stop are not phonetic tools, but stylistic tools. However they are studied in phonetics due to their close connection with pronunciation and the sound side of the language as a speech phenomenon.²

From the point of view of stylistic expression, it is important to use the materials of the language phonetic tool "beyond" the literary orthographic norms. Differences in the pronunciation of words written within the framework of literary orthoepic norms and, in general, combinatorial and positional changes of sounds do not create expression. They are distinguished only by the peculiarity of the everyday speech style. These are the objects of study and research of ordinary methodology.

Phonetic expression tools are mainly the following:³

1. Vowel lengthening. By lengthening a vowel in a certain word, the speaker exaggerates the meaning of the word in which this vowel is involved, draws attention to it, and imposes an additional meaning on this word during speech, thus creates an expression. For example: *Menga achchig‘idan **bo‘lsiiiiin**, menga tovuqligidan, yangi **sousligidaaaan*** (Hot lunch);

2. With a strong pronunciation of the vowel (emphasis). In this case, the speaker gives a tone of tension to his speech, indicates that the idea is firm and reliable, emphasizes the distinction of the identified from another type, and thus imposes an additional task on the whole sentence: *Kiyimlar yangimi? **Yo‘q!!!** Men Perwoll bilan yuvaman.* (Perwol);

3. By doubling the consonant, the speaker expresses his attitudes and feelings towards the object of thought, tries to strengthen the meaning, draws attention to the word with a doubled consonant: ***Kokka kolla**, o‘z ritmingni yoq.* (Coca cola);

4. In addition to changing the content of the sentence (declaration, exclamation, question) through the tone, it expresses such things as pitch, cut, jerk, pity, joy, and joy. So, intonation serves to strengthen and exaggerate the meaning. For example: *Qo‘lda emas, **og‘izda** eriydi.* (M&M’s shokoladi), *Futbol **Lay’s** bilan mazali* (Lay’s chipslari);

5. A pause can serve to express an idea with a certain purpose. An example of this is when a pause indicates thinking, hesitation, joy, fear, continuous thought. *Sezgirlarda san'at. Haqiqiy... Sof... Mukammal...* (Kia avtomobili);

6. Pause and logical emphasis together affect the meaning of the sentence, serve to show what is emphasized. *Yetakchi, ishonchli, innovatsion* (Beeline), *Tomoqmi? Mana dori oldim. Sizga oddiy xo'rozqand emas haqiqiy dori kerak, Septolete* (Septolete);

7. The tone of caressing is expressed by changing the sound. *Yoydam beyadi* (Galavit dori reklamasi);

8. By changing the sound and lengthening the vowel, purposes such as caressing, caressing, softening the situation, and persuading to a certain work are realized. *Voy, Sendayam Veyonami? Qanaqasi? Menda olchaligi, sendachi? Shokoladli. Menda esa, bamisoli bananli bulucha* (Velona);

9. By dividing the word into syllables and pronouncing it, meanings such as tension, serious affirmation or denial are expressed: “*juda zo'r ekan-ku*”, *tovuqni “qanday qilib bunday mazali tayyorlash mumkin”, “bu tovuqni rostdan ham o'zing pishirdingmi?”* *Hamma gap tovuq tanlashda siz Saxovat tovuqlaridan yeng. Qanaqa tovuq? Sa-xo-vat!* (Saxovat tovuqlari).

The transition of advertising to the perlocutionary stage can also be attributed to speech expressions that are meaningless and do not carry special lexical meaning. In this situation, the pragmatic effect in the discourse is ensured by exclamations. For example, a drink of Coca-Cola may initially activate the feeling of thirst visually in the participant of the discourse, but this feeling can be triggered again by saying: Hey, whoosh! It is possible to further strengthen it through a speech. In this case, the information carried by the visual receptors causes a stimulus reaction in exchange for the sound of the auditory receptors, which means the hissing sound typical of the bursting of gas bubbles heard when

opening a cola package, and thereby transmits the information of "carbonated sweet water" to the brain.

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